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PII: S1385-8947(17)31119-1

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.06.167>

Reference: CEJ 17248

To appear in: *Chemical Engineering Journal*

Received Date: 4 April 2017

Revised Date: 27 June 2017

Accepted Date: 28 June 2017

Please cite this article as: C. Casado, R. Timmers, A. Sergejevs, C.T. Clarke, D.W.E. Allsopp, C.R. Bowen, R. van Grieken, J. Marugán, Design and validation of a led-based high intensity photocatalytic reactor for quantifying activity measurements, *Chemical Engineering Journal* (2017), doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2017.06.167>

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**DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF A LED-BASED HIGH INTENSITY
PHOTOCATALYTIC REACTOR FOR QUANTIFYING ACTIVITY
MEASUREMENTS**

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ABSTRACT

Ultraviolet light emitting diodes (UV-LEDs) are attracting the interest of researchers for the design of compact photoreactors due to their energy efficiency, life expectancy, design flexibility, and easily tuned intensity and emission wavelength. However, due to the quasi-point source nature and viewing angle dependence of these illumination sources, the light distribution in LED based reactors can be highly inhomogeneous if the locations of the LEDs in the reactor are not carefully designed. This work describes the design of a novel standardized reactor for accurate measurements of the efficiency of photocatalytic materials under well-controlled lighting conditions. For standardized kinetic studies, it is necessary to ensure that a homogeneous radiation distribution is

achieved over the catalyst surface. UV irradiation calculations involving rigorous solution of the radiative transport equation have been performed to compute the incident radiation at each point of the reactor geometry. Homogeneity calculations over the catalytic surface have been analysed for a range of LED configurations, diameter and distance of the catalyst surface with excellent agreement with measurements. We demonstrate that for many of the configurations and distances examined a poor homogeneity over the catalyst surface is obtained if the LED configuration is not carefully designed. The optimized reactor was built and predictions of the numerical model were validated against spectrophotometric measurements. The designed reactor can be also operated for the determination of the activity of photocatalytic materials in a slurry under very high radiation fluxes. The reactor model was validated with rigorous inclusion of absorption and scattering phenomena under highly demanding conditions of high incident radiation intensities. The developed design provides a novel route for quantitative assessment of photocatalytic materials and reactions.

KEYWORDS

Photocatalytic reactor, LEDs, RTE modelling, cinnamic acid, TiO₂, water treatment.

1. INTRODUCTION

During the last decades, photocatalysis has been shown to be a promising technology, and its principles and potential applications have been investigated in depth. However, there remain a number of challenges in its development for water treatment applications on a high volume and high throughput scale. Mass transfer limitations, elucidation of intermediate products of degradation, low quantum efficiency or deactivation of catalyst are just some of challenges [1]. However, the optimum design and operational

conditions of photoreactors remains a major concern for the development of industrial-scale photocatalytic processes [2–4].

An efficient photoreactor requires an efficient and durable light source. The recent rapid advances in light emitting diode (LED) technology, including high brightness devices emitting ultraviolet (UV) light has made possible a new paradigm for a wide range of lighting applications including photocatalysis [5,6]. The energy conversion efficiency of visible range LED has increased exponentially and they now compete with traditional light sources in most applications. Ultraviolet LED (UV-LED) technology is also following this development path and are increasing in efficiency and decreasing in price every year [7,8]. There are several advantages of UV-LEDs technology over the classical ultraviolet light irradiation sources [9]. They avoid the problem of mercury pollution of UV-A black lights and UV-C germicidal lamps, they have higher energy efficiency, are more robust and have longer life time. Although the emission power can decay with time (ca. 5% per operating year), the life expectancy of LEDs based on maintaining at least 50% of the original light output is approximately 50,000 h, which is five times longer life than Hg-vapour lamps [10]. LED heat production is low compared with traditional lamps [11], and they also offer a good linearity of the emitted light intensity with electrical current and therefore energy consumption. Moreover, in terms of reactor design, UV-LEDs offer interesting options in terms of design flexibility since they are available with monochromatic irradiation, can be used for operation in a pulsed regime at high frequencies and are easily programmable [4,12,13]. The use of UV-LEDs has therefore attracted the interest of researchers and have been used in the design of compact photoreactors for gaseous and aqueous applications [14–17], thereby suggesting that LEDs will be the future of illumination in photocatalytic reactors. However, due to the limited view angle of these emission sources and their quasi-point source nature, the light distribution obtained in reactors illuminated by LEDs can be

highly inhomogeneous if the distribution of LEDs within the reactor is not carefully designed. Levine et al. [10] reported that a lower level of photo-degradation was obtained in a reactor working with LEDs in comparison with a conventional black-light fluorescent lamp, with comparable emission, attributing this behaviour to the poorer homogeneity of the LED sources. Similar conclusions have been also reported in a recent work [18] analysing the photonic efficiency of different LED configurations in comparison with a diffuse UV-A mercury fluorescent lamp of similar emission power and spectrum. The work showed if light homogeneity is not carefully considered in reactor design the improvement in energy efficiency based on the higher electrical energy to light conversion of an LED can be counteracted by a decrease in the photonic efficiency of the photocatalytic process.

The lack of knowledge about the homogeneity of the light distribution present in a photoreactor can lead to erroneous analysis of the reaction rates obtained in photocatalytic processes. For slurry systems, the absorption profile present in a given volume is inherent to the nature of light inside the reacting media and must be known for correct interpretation of the degradation rates within the reactor. When the catalyst particles, for example TiO_2 , are immobilized on a surface, the challenge in designing an efficient photocatalytic reactor becomes one of simultaneously optimizing both the area covered by photocatalytic particles and the light distribution. LEDs currently available in the market can have very high irradiance, which may lead to a reduction in the reaction time needed to reach a degradation target, however the dependence of the photocatalytic reaction rate on the absorbed energy can become non-linear at high incident optical power densities.

To analyse these factors, computational fluid dynamics (CFD) is a promising instrument for the design, optimization, and scale-up of photocatalytic systems. In previous work [19], a lab-scale annular reactor was modelled and integrated the hydrodynamics,

species mass transport, light intensity distribution and reaction kinetics within the reactor with results in good agreement with experimental data. CFD capabilities have been also demonstrated by other research groups using traditional UV-light sources [20–22]. More recently, published reports have included the application of CFD tools for the evaluation of irradiance distribution with LEDs arrays sources and LED-based photoreactor designs [23–27]. Most of these reports have focused of TiO₂ supported reactors and the use of simplified models for light distribution calculations. In this work we present a model-based design and optimization of a novel photocatalytic reactor using numerical simulations based on rigorous solution of the Radiative Transport Equation (RTE) to calculate the UV incident radiation at each point of the geometry. The presented reactor has been designed for standardized measurements of immobilized photocatalyst and photocatalytic films. This application requires not only an optimum efficiency in the use of light but also a well-defined, and finely tuned light output over a wide range of intensities with an homogeneous irradiation of the complete catalyst surface being tested. The model-based optimization of the reactor will allow the determination of the optimal geometry of the reactor, catalyst support and the LED array configuration, and the predictions are successfully validated by experimental spectroradiometric measurements. In addition, the designed reactor can be also operated for the determination of the activity of photocatalytic materials in slurry under very high radiation fluxes. For this application, the reactor model has been also validated with a rigorous resolution of the absorption and scattering phenomena under highly demanding conditions of high incident radiation intensities.

2. METHODS

2.1 LED board design and homogeneity tests

In order to design a LED array that homogeneously illuminates the supported catalyst, four different configurations of LEDs were considered, see Figure 1. The selected configurations were chosen based in several constraints: i) the catalyst support will have a circular geometry; ii) the size of the catalytic surface will be of few centimetres, enough to get measurable reaction rates but still requiring small amounts of catalysts for quick lab-scale measurements; iii) the dimensions of the LEDs integrated circuit board will be limited to the size of the lab-scale reactor and catalytic surface; and, iv) a high irradiation power, homogeneous over the catalytic surface, is required for the photocatalytic experiments. For these reasons, the configurations studied included different numbers of LEDs, and therefore, different spacing between devices, distributed as regularly as possible over a circular space. The homogeneity in the irradiation of a catalyst surface was evaluated for different distances from the light source, ranging from 40 to 80 mm and also different diameter of the catalyst holder (40 and 60 mm). LEDs specifications were obtained from commercially available components (LED Engin, model LZ1-00U600, bin code H) with a minimum radiant flux of 585 mW at 1000 mA in a narrow wavelength range centred at 365 nm.

To assess the irradiation homogeneity over the catalyst surface, an additional variation of the 36-D configuration was also simulated (Configuration 36-D2), by modifying the light output of the inner 12 LEDs; see the red squares in Figure 2. Table 1 shows the total LED emission of the studied cases. Unless otherwise indicated, all the homogeneity studies were carried out setting the LEDs intensity to 80 % of the maximum value of 800 mA.

2.2 Photoreactor construction

Based on the model-based optimization, a LED board, shown in Figure 2, was assembled with the configuration 36-D (Figure 1). The LEDs were grouped in 12 different channels, each comprising 3 LEDs connected in series, for independent regulation of the electrical intensity in order to finely tune the emitted radiation power. The photoreactor consisted of a Pyrex glass beaker equipped with a cooling jacket to allow close temperature control during the experiments since the oxygen saturation concentration is sensitive to temperature fluctuations [28]. The inner vessel of the reactor had a diameter of 80 mm, a height of 80 mm, and a wall thickness of 2.5 mm. The outer vessel had a diameter of 110 mm, a height of 95 mm, and a wall thickness of 3 mm. The catalytic materials were located at a fixed distance from the light source by the use of PTFE frame. The catalyst holder had a diameter of 40 mm which was based on the results of the radiation homogeneity test shown later. The frame had six holes with a diameter of 8 mm to allow oxygen bubbling in order to ensure constant oxygen saturation of the reaction liquid, withdrawal of samples, to measure pH, temperature, oxygen and pollutant concentration and any other parameters required to follow the photocatalytic reaction. The LED circuit board and its cooling unit were bolted to the upper part of the frame. A rigid black lid was bolted to a rigid black cylindrical structure and was incorporated to form a cover that blocked radiation from external uncontrolled light sources and to provide mechanical support to the whole setup.

Figure 3 shows a schematic representation of the constant volume batch reactor with a frame to hold the photocatalyst, the LEDs board and the cooling unit required for the dissipation of the heat release from the LEDs.

2.3 Radiation simulations and validation

To simulate the distribution of the radiation, the reactor geometry was defined to have the exact dimensions of the physical prototype shown in Figure 3. The three

dimensional (3D) space was discretised into approximately 350000 structured and unstructured volume cells, corresponding to a mean cell volume of $1.15 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3$.

Testing of the model revealed this number of cells was optimum for achieving mesh-independent predictions. The model reactor geometry and mesh are represented in Figure 4.

Validation of the model predictions was carried out in the lower irradiance range with an emission power lower than 2.53 W, see Table 2, to maximize the sensitivity of the experimental radiation measurements and at a distance of 7 cm from the LED sources. The 36-D2 configuration, with a decreased emission intensity from the 12 inner LEDs was used in the validation, as this configuration provided good result in terms of homogeneity. Table 2 summarizes the different emission settings employed for validation of the radiation model.

Experimental radiation fluxes at the catalyst surface were measured by replacing the catalyst holder by a disk, designed to fix the radiation sensor at different positions, see Figure 5. The radiation measurements were taken at 13 different positions, with the geometrical centre acting as the origin in analysing the results.

A UV-A radiation meter (gigahertz-Optik x97, sensor UV3710) was used to measure the radiation flux. Experimental data were compared with the results of the numerical simulations for model validation.

2.4 CFD Photoreactor Radiation Modelling

Radiation transfer was modelled using commercial software (Ansys Fluent 14.5, Ansys Inc.). The LEDs were simulated as 1.6 mm diameter surfaces following the specifications of the vendor [29]. Rigorous radiation computations require the resolution of the radiative transfer equation (RTE). This integro-differential equation describes the traveling of light rays with energy (intensity) loss due to absorption and out-scattering

and energy gain due to in-scattering of energy along their trajectories. The discrete ordinate method (DOM) was used to solve the RTE, allowing the evaluation of the radiation field at any point inside the reactor.

The angular discretisation was set to 25×25 divisions to avoid the “ray effect”. The ray effect arises from approximating the continuously varying angular nature of radiation by a specified set of discrete angular directions. If the angular discretization is not enough, radiation intensities tend to concentrate in the discrete directions [30,31]. Spatial discretisation becomes especially important when modelling LEDs, since each LED emits light into a conical volume, and a minimum number of discrete directions is needed to capture the emission angle accurately and capture the angle of viewing. A surface emission model was used for the emitting LEDs, set as transparent exterior walls with external irradiation. An emission cone angle of 85 degrees was set according to the LED specifications [29]. All the remaining walls were set as zero-thickness and also semi-transparent. The temperature was fixed to 1K in all domains to inactivate calculations of radiation emission, reducing the computational cost of the model at high spatial resolution. Since solving the RTE for each individual wavelength can be computationally expensive, only the UV-A band in the range from 320-400 nm was solved.

Modelling of radiation transport and volumetric rates of absorption in photocatalytic suspension were carried out considering the optical properties (such as absorption and scattering coefficients and scattering phase function) of a specified catalytic material. This was undertaken using P25 TiO₂ (Evonik Industries) using the optical properties taken from the literature [32] at the wavelength of the maximum emission of the LEDs (370 nm). The scattering phase function was described using the Henyey and Greenstein equation, non-available in the native software but was introduced through a user defined function (UDF). Air and water media were considered transparent in the UV-A range,

with no interaction with radiation. Second order discretisation was used for solving the RTE. Convergence of the numerical solution was ensured by monitoring the scaled residuals to a criterion of at least 10^{-6} for the incident radiation. Additionally, the variables of interest have been monitored at different surfaces of the computational domain as an indicator of convergence, defined as at least 50 iterations without changes. A more detailed description of the equations and the radiation modelling approach can be found elsewhere [19].

2.5 Photocatalytic experiments

Experimental evaluation of the reactor performance was carried out using cinnamic acid (CA) as a test compound representative of the aromatic pollutants usually present in agro-industrial wastewaters [33]. These compounds, present in effluents and landfills, are difficult to degrade and toxic for most microorganism present in water [34], and are of increasing environmental concern [35–37]. Cinnamic acid (99%, Sigma Aldrich) was carefully dissolved in 250 mL of Milli-Q® water ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$) at an initial concentration of 50 mg L^{-1} . Reactions were carried out at constant temperature of 20°C . A continuous air supply provides enough oxygen to keep saturation conditions at this temperature. The natural pH of the system was used without further adjustment. Mixing was ensured by stirring with a PTFE plain bar of dimensions $8\times 40 \text{ mm}$ and rotating at 250 rpm. Different concentrations of P25 TiO_2 (0.01 g L^{-1} , 0.05 g L^{-1} and 0.1 g L^{-1}) were added to the reactor. The reaction evolution was followed by withdrawal of 1 mL samples at different time intervals over 1 hour, keeping the total volume of samples below 5% of the total volume. Under these conditions, constant reaction volume, good mixing behaviour and constant concentration of oxygen can be safely assumed. These

three assumptions significantly simplify the mathematical modelling of the mass balances and reaction kinetics. Analysis of the samples was carried out after filtration with 0.22 μm regenerated cellulose filters (Serviquimia). A UV/vis spectrophotometer (Biochrom Libra S22) was used to register the absorbance of the samples at 272 nm wavelength, corresponding to the maximum of the absorption of cinnamic acid (spectrum not shown), after a ten-fold dilution. Quantification was carried out after calibration with standards of known composition. The chemical oxygen demand (COD) was determined by means of the standard potassium dichromate method. Total organic carbon (TOC) was analysed using a combustion/non dispersive infrared gas analyser; model TOC-V from Shimadzu.

3. RESULTS

3.1 LEDs Configuration

Four different LED configurations, shown in Figure 1, were studied to examine the homogeneity of the irradiation of a flat surface located at 6 cm from the plane of the LED array. Figure 6 shows the computed results for 12-A, 21-B, 36-C LED configurations. A comparison between the 36 LED configurations 36-C, 36-D1 and 36-D2 was also made and will be shown in a later section. In all cases very high radiant fluxes are achieved, more than two orders of magnitude above the 30 W m^{-2} usually taken as reference for the solar UV irradiance under sunny atmospheric conditions [38]. It is usually considered [39] that very high values of absorbed energy may lead to a reactor working under sub-optimal conditions regarding the use of the light with a square root dependence of the reaction rate versus radiation absorption instead of the linear regime expected for low radiation conditions. However, the simulations reveal that despite the reduction in the energy efficiency the near 100-sun irradiance available from the 36-LED array can increase the absolute reaction rate of the process, thereby

reducing the required treatment time. As will be shown, the easy regulation of the LED output enables the reactor to be operated over a wide range of optical power outputs thereby aiding fuller quantitative studies of photocatalysis.

As the incident radiation over the photocatalytic surface changes between LED configurations, results of the different number of LEDs used in each array type and the global quantification of the radiation homogeneity were carried out by calculating the standard deviation of the irradiance over the catalyst surface, divided by the averaged incident radiation value. The parameter 'relative deviation' was used to compare the homogeneity when the median values are different. For a better understanding of energy distribution, Figure 7 shows the homogeneity for the most different configurations with 12 and 36 LEDs. The relative deviation was also used to capture the shape and homogeneity of the radiation reaching the surface calculated for all the points and represented as surface graphs. Despite the similar values of the global relative deviation values found for these configurations (19.04% and 19.27% respectively for 5 cm distance, Figure 7a and Figure 7b, and 10.60% and 10.77% for 7 cm distance, Figure 7c and Figure 7d), the non-uniformity in the illumination becomes more marked when 12 LEDs are used. Moreover, preferential emission directions are found, due to the smaller number of LEDs used and the space between devices. In this distribution, 12-A, a higher amount of light is reaching the catalyst surface in the regions where LEDs are present, the overlap of the emission angle of each LED causes the illumination of the whole catalyst disk, but is centred in the directions on which the LEDs have been located (see Figure 1a).

Next, the result for the average incident radiation reaching the catalyst surface, the relative deviation and an energy utilization factor defined as the fraction of the total emitted light reaching the catalyst surface was calculated for every condition and represented in Figure 8. Results for 12-A, 21-B and 36-C LED configurations showed

that for a 6 cm diameter photocatalyst surface the 12-A configuration offers slightly more uniform irradiation when the distance to the LED source is less than 6 cm (Figure 8). This tendency changes for larger LED-catalyst separations when the 36-C configuration gives slightly improved homogeneity. The circumference of the cone into which a LED emits changes with the distance to the photocatalytic surface. As the distance between adjacent LEDs changes, these circumferences overlap causing the optical homogeneity to occur at different distances for the different LED configurations. However, the variations in homogeneity for these configurations are less than 3% at the same LED-catalyst separation. The increase in homogeneity becomes more marked as the LED-catalyst separation is doubled from 4 cm, where the relative intensity variation across the catalyst is 26%, to 8 cm where the relative intensity varies only 7.5% (Figure 8b). Optimization of the distance at which the catalytic surface is located was found to be critical to uniform illumination of the catalyst, and is therefore important to quantification of reaction rates. However, in industrial applications energy efficiency becomes the critical factor in determining the optimum LED-to-catalyst geometry. For example, when the catalyst frame is placed 4 cm from the LEDs, ~80% of the emitted energy reaches the catalyst surface; although the exact value depends on the LED configuration. Increasing the distance to 8 cm more than 70% of the emitted energy is lost in the planar geometry considered. In terms of energy utilization, when the 36 LEDs are used only 30% of the light emitted reaches this surface when the LED-catalyst separation is 8 cm, although the intensity variation across the photocatalyst is less than 10%. Quantitatively, the predicted integrated intensity reaching the catalyst surface is 2 W for 12 LEDs and 5 W for 36 LEDs, corresponding to power densities of 707 and 1768 W m⁻², when the LED-catalyst separation is 8 cm.

3.1.1. Effect of the diameter of the catalyst disk

Decreasing the catalyst area from 6 cm diameter to 4 cm resulted in a variation in the uniformity of the irradiance of approximately 50 % for all configurations and distances.

As seen in Figure 9, the shape of the deviation is more irregular for 12 LEDs, while 36 LEDs give a more regular but still dome-shaped intensity pattern.

The increase in uniformity compared with the larger diameter frame is larger when the catalyst is placed close to the LED array but becomes less important for larger separations. Overall, there is still a significant improvement in uniformity. With a catalytic surface of 4 cm diameter, for all distances and LED configurations, the variation in uniformity is less than 12.5%. For separations larger than 5 cm, the variation in uniformity is less than 10%, a value low enough to assume homogeneous radiation in kinetic studies.

Selecting the best LED configuration is not a straightforward task, since it requires a compromise between the uniformity of the irradiance and energy efficiency. A significant increase in the homogeneity is reached by decreasing the diameter of the catalytic surface to be tested, but optical energy efficiency decreases significantly. Further, with a 6 cm diameter surface using 12 LEDs in general resulted in smaller values of relative error. For a 4 cm diameter catalytic surface using a 21 LED configuration yields a small increase in the uniformity of the irradiation especially for larger separations. Nevertheless, energy efficiency is reduced when 12 or 21 LEDs are used, compared with 36 LEDs-C, and the global value of optical power (W) reaching the surface is less than 5 W when these configurations are used at any LED-catalyst separation.

3.1.2. 36 LEDs configuration

Due to scope for operating the reactor under very high illumination conditions, up to 100 Suns [40], a detailed study of the conditions needed to achieve uniform irradiance

of the catalyst surface with 36 LEDs array was performed. Different arrangements of the LEDs were considered, notably configuration 36-D, shown in Figure 1, in which the central 12 LEDs have been rotated by 45° relative to the others. The effect of varying the optical power emitted from the 12 inner LEDs was considered as a means for increasing the uniformity of the irradiance reaching the catalyst surface. In this case, only the results for a 4 cm diameter circular catalyst surface are presented, owing to the advantage to uniformity of a smaller disk demonstrated in the previous section. Figure 10 shows the distribution in the incident radiation reaching a catalytic surface at a distance of 6 cm from the different 36 LED configurations shown in Figure 1.

For all the LED-catalyst separations considered the 36-D1 configuration produced more uniform irradiance of the catalyst surface than configuration 36-C. To understand this effect, local non-homogeneities over the surface are presented in Figure 11 for 5 and 7 cm LED-catalyst separations. Compared with Figure 9, where the results for the 36-C configuration are presented, both 36-D1 and 36-D2 produce a flatter, smoother distribution in the intensity reaching the catalyst surface.

For a 4 cm distance between the catalyst surface and the LED board, a condition that maximizes efficient use of the optical power, decreasing the intensity of the inner 12 LEDs reduces the average irradiance, but increases its uniformity by more than 19% compared with configuration 36-C, and by more than 12% when the distance is increased to 5 cm. However, when the LED-catalyst separation exceeds 6 cm the non-uniformity of the irradiance becomes larger than that obtained with configuration 36-C.

Figure 12 shows the energy utilization and intensity variation for the three 36 LED configurations considered. Their energy utilization factors are quite similar, although the 36-D2 configuration is somewhat less efficient than configurations 36-C and 36-D1. LED configuration 36-D2 was chosen for the final design of the LED board, since it combination of 80% of the maximum emission power on the external LEDs and 20% on

the inner LEDs provides pseudo-uniform irradiation of the catalyst surface when the catalyst frame is placed at 7 cm from the LED board. A 7 cm separation gives rise to a deviation from uniform irradiance of less than a 5% over the catalyst whilst preventing immersion of the LEDs into liquid specimens, and can be varied by ± 1 cm without causing significant change in uniformity. Additionally, the ability to vary the emission power of the 36 LEDs individually provides a useful tool to test photocatalysts at different irradiation conditions, including UV-A light fluxes in the order of 2300 W m^{-2} , two orders of magnitude higher than the typical UV-A flux from the Sun.

3.2 Model Validation

To validate the predictions of the numerical simulations, measurements at different light intensities were performed with a total emission of the LEDs system lower than 2.5 W, shown in Table 2. Figure 13 shows a comparison between the measured and simulated radial distribution of the irradiance across the catalyst surface for different percentages of maximum optical power being emitted from the LEDs. Both distributions are an average of the results of the four quadrants of the disk and are in close agreement.

An additional validation test was performed for high emission power, 9.8 W, again using configuration 36-D2. At this high emission Joule heating in the LEDs becomes an important issue, even with the use of a cooling system, and the temperature of the LED circuit board rose by more than 40°C after 1 hour of operation. Figure 14 compares the simulated emission with and without a correction of the emission flux due to LED heating with measurement. The correction to the emission flux is based on the temperature dependence of emitted power provided in the manufacturer's data sheet of the LEDs used (Datasheet LZ1-00UV00 LED, LED Engin Inc., CA, USA), specifically a 20% of reduction in the emission for a 40°C temperature rise. When the reduction in

emitted power with rise in temperature is taken into account the agreement between the CFD results and measurement is excellent. This result demonstrates the need for controlling the operating temperature of UV-LED light sources in fully quantitative characterization of photocatalysis. In this respect, a further consideration is the red-shift the emission peak wavelength with increasing LED temperature, which can alter the absorption of light by the photocatalyst [40].

3.3 Simulation of Photocatalytic Slurries.

In addition to the estimation of the UV-A radiation flux incident to the catalytic surface for the evaluation of immobilized materials, the developed model can be used for determining volumetric rates of photon absorption for the photoreactor operating with photocatalytic slurries. By considering the absorption coefficients of the materials and the catalyst loading, the amount of absorbed light can be estimated, a factor essential to quantification of chemical reaction kinetics. Simulations of reactor operation with P25 TiO₂ were carried out for increasing catalyst loadings (0.01 g L⁻¹, 0.05 g L⁻¹ and 0.1 g L⁻¹) with radiation intensities of 5%, 10%, 20% and 100% of the full optical power of LED configuration 36-D2, with temperature correction of the emitted power. Figure 15 shows that for each catalyst loading the absorption varies linearly with the intensity of the irradiance irrespective of the catalyst loading. As seen in the inset of Figure 15, increasing the catalyst concentration from 0.01 to 0.05 g L⁻¹ leads to a ~2.5 times increase in the absorbed radiation; however further increase in the catalyst concentration to 0.1 g L⁻¹ yields only a very small increase in the absorption of light. This saturation effect is manifested by radiation intensity contours on the vertical plane of symmetry of the reactor (Figure 16). The more rapid absorption in the upper layer of the catalyst, together with light scattering, prevents light penetrating into the lower part when the catalyst loading is above 0.05 g L⁻¹, indicating that optimal operation of the designed

reactor when using a P25 TiO₂ slurry occurs with catalyst loading is $\sim 0.05 \text{ g L}^{-1}$. This value leads to a dimensionless optical thickness (calculated as the product of the optical path and the optical extinction coefficient) of 13.86, a little higher than the optimum value for photocatalytic reactors estimated by Colina-Marquez et al. using a six-flux radiation model [41]. Our simulations neglect any reduction in the absorption of the TiO₂ due to saturation of excited quantum states (the Moss-Burstein effect). This will have the effect of increasing the optical thickness catalyst needed in practice. Apart from the increase and subsequent saturation of the absorbed optical power, the only other changes in the radiation balance are concomitant rapid reductions with increase in catalyst loading in light loss through the bottom of the reactor and through the part of the reactor walls in contact with the liquid specimen.

3.4 Photocatalytic reactions

Figure 17 shows measurements of cinnamic acid degradation for the three different catalyst concentrations considered in the previous section using LED configuration 36-D2 with the intensity LEDs as parameter. Using the highest radiation intensity with 0.1 g L^{-1} TiO₂ loading 90% degradation of the pollutant is achieved after 60 min of irradiation, confirming the feasibility of the photocatalytic remediation of this kind of recalcitrant contaminant. Both photolytic and dark adsorption experiments with 0.1 g L^{-1} of catalyst (not shown) led to negligible decrease in the cinnamic acid concentration, confirming the photocatalytic nature of the process.

In all cases the measured degradation rates followed an exponential dependence corresponding to a pseudo-first order kinetic model, especially the lower conversion rates for which it can be assumed that, for the initial reactor conditions, intermediate species do not interfere with the degradation process. For longer irradiation

experiments, COD and TOC results lead to values of the pseudo-first order kinetic constant half than those of the cinnamic acid removal, confirming the accumulation of intermediate species before the complete mineralization.

The measured kinetic constants correlate with the estimates of the averaged absorption of radiation in the reactor, as shown Figure 18, to provide further evidence of the photocatalytic nature of the degradation. This behaviour is commonly attributed to the relative increase of the second order reaction rate of electron/hole recombination under high irradiation fluxes [42,43].

Although the increase in the reaction rate is not proportional to the LED intensity, Figure 19 shows that the use of high emission fluxes, such as those provided by LEDs, enables a high percentage of cinnamic acid removal in a reduced irradiation time, a beneficial attribute in applications of photocatalysis to disinfection and water purification.

For reactors operating under high optical thickness, where unilluminated regions can occur in a reactor, the type of CFD analysis of the energy absorbed by the catalyst described here would allow identification of the conditions in which the increases in the energy consumption and catalyst concentration does not yield improvement in the degradation rate. For example, in the designed reactor, 78% removal of cinnamic acid is achieved in 60 minutes with a suspension of 0.05 g L^{-1} of TiO_2 and 60% of the UV radiation power available, while doubling the catalyst loading causes an increase to only 85% removal of the contaminant.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A model-based design and optimization of a novel reactor for quantitative measurements of photocatalytic reactions has been presented. The design process involves rigorous solution of the Radiative Transport Equation (RTE) to calculate the

UV radiation at each point of the geometry, and has been validated via measurements of the rate of degradation rates of cinnamic acid using different concentrations of TiO_2 catalyst and wide range of optical power levels. Agreement between the CFD results and measurement is excellent. The model has taken into account the quasi-point source and directional nature of LED emission when identifying reactor geometries in which a variation in the irradiance over the catalyst surface was less than 7.5%, while a level low enough for accurate determination of reaction kinetics, could be improved on by more fully optimising the number and locations of the LEDs on their circuit board and fine tuning the electrical energy applied to them.

The model can also account for the decrease in LED efficiency with increasing operating temperature, an attribute needed in determining the absorbed radiation and hence predict the energy efficiency of reactor designs. In particular, the absorbed radiation of different titanium oxide suspensions was also calculated, allowing the identification of the optimum catalyst loading. The analysis of the measured degradation of cinnamic acid with different catalyst loadings and illumination conditions complied with the theoretical influence of absorbed radiation on the reaction rate, confirming numerical simulation as a reliable model-based approach for the simulation and optimization of photocatalytic reactors. The developed design provides a new route for robust and quantitative assessment of photocatalytic materials and reactions.

Acknowledgements.

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the European Commission under FP7 project 309846, “Photocatalytic Materials for the Destruction of Recalcitrant Organic Industrial Waste (PCATDES)”. Cintia Casado also acknowledges MINECO for her FPI grant (BES-2012-056661).

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Figure Captions

Figure 1. LED configurations studied. A) 12 LED configuration, 12-A, B) 21 LED configuration, 21-B, C) 36 LED configuration, 36-C and D) 36 LED configuration, 36-D.

Figure 2. LED configuration for test reactor.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the designed batch reactor.

Figure 5. Experimental set-up for accurate radiation measurements.

Figure 6. Incident radiation over a 6 cm catalytic surface located at 6 cm from LEDs source. A) 12 LED configuration, B) 21 LED configuration, C) 36 LED configuration-C.

Figure 7. Deviation over the average incident radiation for light reaching a catalytic surface of 6 cm diameter. A) 12 LED configuration emission at 5 cm to multi-LED source, B) 36 LED configuration - C at 5 cm to LED source, C) 12 LED configuration

emission at 7 cm, D) B) 36 LED configuration - C at 7 cm.

Figure 8. Results for a catalytic surface of 6 cm diameter. A) Radiation reaching the catalyst surface for different LEDs configuration. Numbers over the columns represent the energy utilization factor. B) Variation in the relative deviation (homogeneity) over

the surface with LEDs to surface distance and LEDs configuration.

Figure 9. Deviation over the average incident radiation for light reaching a catalytic surface of 4 cm diameter. A) 12-A LED configuration and B) 36-C LED configuration, both with a 5 cm LED board-catalyst separation C) 12-A configuration and D) 36-C,

both with a 7 cm LED board-catalyst separation.

Figure 10. Incident Radiation over a 4 cm catalytic surface located at 6 cm from LED array: A) configuration 36-C; B) configuration 36-D1; C) configuration 36-D2.

Figure 11. Deviation over the average incident radiation for light reaching a catalytic surface of 4 cm diameter. A) 36 LEDs-D1 at 5 cm to LED source, B) 36 LEDs-D2 at 5

cm to LED source, C) 36 LEDs-D1 at 7 cm, D) 36 LEDs-D2 at 7 cm.

Figure 12. Results for a catalytic surface of 4 cm diameter. A) Radiation, W , reaching the catalyst surface for different 36 - LEDs configuration. Numbers over the columns represent the energy utilization factor. B) Variation in the relative deviation (homogeneity) over the surface with LEDs to surface distance and LEDs configuration.

Figure 13. Radiation validation for low LEDs emission. The points show the measured values; lines are results of the CFD simulations.

Figure 14. Radiation validation for high LEDs emission. The dots are experimental values. The lines are results of CFD simulations, with and without LEDs emission

correction due to a temperature rise.

Figure 15. Absorbed light in the reactor volume for different light intensities and catalyst concentrations. Inset) Absorption ratio calculated between the absorbed energy

and the emission value.

Figure 16. Incident radiation in the reactor for the maximum emission of LED configuration 36-D2 with temperature correction. The contours presented lie the vertical symmetry plane of the reactor. Upper row: Full reactor domain. Lower row: Liquid reaction volume. The results have rotational symmetry round the reactor. A) 0 g L⁻¹, B)

0.01 g L⁻¹ TiO₂, C) 0.05 g L⁻¹ TiO₂, D) 0.1 g L⁻¹ TiO₂.

Figure 17. Cinnamic acid degradation under different light intensities and catalyst loadings.

Figure 18. Dependence on light absorption of the first order kinetic constants for the degradation of cinnamic acid.

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Figure 19. Cinnamic acid removal at different times obtained under various LEDs power emission and catalyst concentration.

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Table 1. LED emission for the configurations tested during homogeneity analysis.

UV-A EMISSION POWER (W)	
(0.585 W/LED 100% Intensity 1 A)	Total Emission (W), 80% Intensity
12 LEDs-A	5.62
21 LEDs-B	9.84
36 LEDs, Configuration 36-C	16.87
36 LEDs, Configuration 36-D1	16.87
36 LEDs, Configuration 36-D2*	12.65

*Inner 12 LEDs operated at 20% of their maximum and the outer 24 LEDs operated at 80% of their maximum intensity

Table 2. Settings for radiation model validation

UV-A EMISSION POWER(W)					
Intensity Percentage (0.585 W/LED 100% Intensity)	<u>Internal LEDs</u>		<u>External LEDs</u>		TOTAL 36 LEDs
	1 LED	12 LEDs	1 LED	24 LEDs	
Configuration 36-D2 (External LEDs 80%, Internal LEDs 20%)	0.117	1.406	0.468	11.25	12.65
Configuration 36-D2 (Temperature Correction)*	0.091	1.096	0.365	8.77	9.87
20 % Emission of Configuration 36-D2	0.023	0.281	0.094	2.25	2.53
15 % Emission of Configuration 36-D2	0.018	0.211	0.070	1.69	1.90
10 % Emission of Configuration 36-D2	0.012	0.141	0.047	1.13	1.27
5 % Emission of Configuration 36-D2	0.006	0.070	0.023	0.56	0.63

* Includes the temperature correction based in experimental measurements, only needed for high emission fluxes.

HIGHLIGHTS

- Radiation homogeneity over a catalyst surface studied for a range of LED arrays
- Construction of an optimized LED-based photocatalytic reactor for catalyst testing
- Novel design for assessment and characterization of photocatalytic materials.
- Radiation model successfully validated with experimental measurements
- Determination of absorbed energy and optimal concentration for TiO₂ suspensions

